

STANDARDIZATION TO ENSURE PRODUCT QUALITY SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

At all stages of human development, the concept of "quality" is special approach, different definitions are given to it, but the essence is exactly the same It is understood that the thing satisfies the specified need.

With the emergence of human society, "the establishment of rules and there was a demand for the emergence of "application". Writing, counting system, monetary unit, different units of measurement - all these are the first shoots of standardization. As production progressed, standardization also progressed. And this influenced the rapid growth of production forces, In ancient Rome, water fountains were made of pipes of exactly the same diameter was It is correct that the treated stones should be of specific (standard) sizes made it possible to build Egyptian ehrams with a geometric shape. One of the Ehrams stones weighing several tons are so accurately worked and densely packed together laid so that even a needle does not pass between them. 90 m high Babylon 85 million in the construction of the tower. This is evidenced by the fact that single standard bricks were used shows that there were certain rules and procedures in brick baking. Standardization is repetitive in science, technology and economics to find a solution to the problems and arrange them at a favorable level in a certain area is a referral activity. There are many standards and serial production determined for the most important products to be released. Machine in standards, tools, weapons, various materials and types, types, models, shapes, sizes, in relation to them technical requirements, as well as test methods, placement and storage, en route transportation rules are defined. Standard units of measurement, designations, practical technical terms and definitions are also shown, without which the quality of the product cannot be clearly defined. Each standard has a number and a year of approval. For example, the 1962 Standard on Basic Definitions of Permissibility and Transfers if approved, it is defined as follows: GOST 7713-62. Here GOST — State standard, the four digits on the left (7713) are the serial number of the standard, the last two and the number (62) indicates the year of approval of the standard. The main purpose of standardization is: science and technology acceleration of development, society's production and labor productivity increase,

improve product quality and ensure its acceptable level, people improvement of management of the economy and approval of the produced product establishment of nomenclature, product design and production development of specialization, as well as rationalization of production funds use, saving material and labor resources, health and labor ensuring security, international economic, technical and cultural cooperation development. On standardization to achieve these goals activities should be focused on solving the following issues:

Based on comprehensive standardization of finished product quality final products, raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and components setting requirements for product quality characteristics. -System of uniform indicators of product quality, its test and control methods and tools and product requirements taking into account the level of reliability, its nature and conditions of use development with. -Ensuring convenient product quality and types of models and sizes product design in order to eliminate the redundancy of variety and establishing standard requirements and methods in production. -Production specialization, complex production processes mechanization and automation, interchangeability It is important to raise the level, use and repair the product effectively development of industrial product unification as a condition.

Ensuring the unit of measurement and accuracy in the country, high accuracy improvement of measuring methods and tools. -Unified system of documents and important fields of science and technology establishing uniform terms and definitions,

Labor safety, nature protection and use of natural resources establishing systems of standards in the field of improvement. Standardization is the production of a certain material in the near future ensures development and all enterprises improve the quality of their products forces to raise the level. We use a lot of things (tools, devices, machines), cars, etc. in life, construction and technology. The work during this period, these items fail, wear out, and become unusable. Therefore, in order to re-use items, repair them, that is, it is necessary to replace their broken parts with new ones. Only if the dimensions of the replacement part are correct, it will fit into the product, otherwise, you will have to resize that part. That's it it can be concluded that the repair work of the broken parts of the products sizes that are known and enforced for ease of use production is necessary. This system of dimensions is called standardization. The most important importance of standardization is that it has a necessary effect on the rate and level of development of production. Of this and for the standardization of science and technology and practical experiences relies on achievements. Hence, the importance of standardization is that ease and convenience in replacing broken parts with another is to create.

Safety of products, works and services - product development release, use (its use), storage, transportation, realization and disposal processes, performed works, rendered services is a state, which affects human life, health, environment, legal, physical the way related to the possibility of damage to the property of individuals and the state there will be no risk that cannot be taken; Regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation are technical regulations, normative documents on standardization, sanitary, veterinary - sanitary, phytosanitary rules and norms, urban planning norms and rules, environmental norms and regulations and technical regulation other documents in the field; General technical regulation - in the field of technical regulation, one Mandatory requirements for the

safety of a group of products, works and services defining regulatory document; Technical barriers to trade - related to the safety of products, works and services in regulatory documents in the field of technical regulation of mandatory requirements arising in trade as a result of existing differences or changes barriers. Technically, regulation means production and consumption to the established requirements for the safety of products between the fields, production production, storage, transportation, sale, application, and use activities issues of relationship formation related to the verification of requirements execution set is meant. In this case, the market is a business and product cycle on the one hand freedom, on the other hand, to produce products, provide services and regulated through compliance approval processes and other requirements. In practice, regulation is product safety and related processes regulatory legal document in the technical direction that defines the necessary requirements for is formed as From an economic point of view, technical norms are known a powerful tool for implementing economic policy with a share of conditionality. By means of management by technical standards, organization of markets or vice versa elimination, determination of necessary levels of development, other areas launching new industrial lines while maintaining their development and so on other activities can be done. Technical regulation increases the competitiveness of products, modernization of production and products and their production ensuring the safety of processes and foreign economic interests of the country it is an important direction of priority in protection. It is known that the economic infrastructure of our Republic is international a number of works are being carried out on integration into the society. In this process the main task is to solve existing technical obstacles in trade. Therefore, technical The activities carried out on regulation are very important have Because the World Trade Organization is the unhindered access to the world market reasonable application of technical requirements is necessary to meet the requirements. In accordance with the procedure established in all CIS countries, also in Uzbekistan Many documents establishing mandatory requirements have been implemented, and this is in turn, in production and service, as well as foreign trade creates certain technical obstacles in their relations. Including such documents standards, sanitary and hygiene rules, construction norms and rules, pharmacopeia substances, phytosanitary, environmental, fire, veterinary, energy, traffic regulations are included. Such a system is international experience and world trade "Technical Barriers to Trade" (STT) and "Sanitary and Phytosanitary" of the organization measures" (SFS) are contrary to the requirements of the Agreement. These Agreements is based on voluntary application of standards, and mandatory requirements are different embodied in the document. Such a document is called "Technical Regulation". To enter the World Trade Organization in our republic the current policy, first of all, the products being produced aimed at increasing competitiveness and export potential. Uzbekistan is a state system of technical regulation Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on technical regulation "Technical Regulation" entered into force on April 23, 2009 The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains 4 chapters and 28 articles. Adoption of this law will internationalize the existing standardization system brought another step closer to the practice. The purpose of the law is the safety of products, works and services regulate relations in the field of setting, applying and fulfilling mandatory requirements consists of putting "On technical regulation" of the Republic of Uzbekistan Law on health and life of citizens, environmental protection and

national defense and aimed at creating a mechanism for ensuring national security. The purpose of adopting the law is to maintain the old technical economy transition to a new economic management system and technical regulation, and also a technical member of the World Trade Organization (WTO). prevention of obstacles and the requirements of the Agreements of this organization are complete is aimed at ensuring its implementation, and this, in turn, is the work of our country opportunity for producers to compete equally with foreign partners creates. According to the law, in the development of technical regulations, products, works and national and international regulations defining the security criteria of services documents are used and technical as an evidence base in technical regulations the texts of normative documents in the field of regulation in whole or in part is set to be brought. "On technical regulation" of the Republic of Uzbekistan Law on products, works and services with the adoption of technical regulations that the use of normative documents on standardization becomes voluntary specified (Article 22). That is, technical products, works and services if the regulations are approved, new work on standardization normative documents are voluntary for use. The main purpose, tasks and principles of technical regulation Technically, the main goal of regulation is the life of citizens and protection of health, natural and legal persons and state property, environment protection, safety of animals and plants, as well as consumers aimed at eliminating actions aimed at misleading consumers is to achieve adoption of technical regulations. The main tasks of technical regulation are as follows: Ensuring the safety of human life and health, legal entities, individuals and state property; The environment is protected, as well as natural resources ensure its use; Elimination of technical obstacles in trade; Consumers regarding the safety of products, works and services prevention of distracting actions. The main principles of technical regulation are as follows:

mandatory application of technical regulations;

uniform application of technical regulations;

national and international in the field of technical regulation of technical regulations compliance with regulatory documents;

technical regulations, the procedure for their development, adoption and publication openness of information about.

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